

“WORK FROM HOME”: AN ALTERNATE WORK TREND**Mrs. Ekta Abhishek Chawda***Assistant Professor**Achievers College of Commerce & Management***Abstract:**

The big crisis we have faced in 2020 was Corona. Due to this the people bound to work from home (i.e. online work). The situation created by CORONA diseases that no one is allowed to touch or meet a person nearby. Henceforth, people are helpless to work from home. Due to this there are many good points where people have accepted the online work at the same time it is worthwhile enough to work from home as it is convenient to work, save time, no travelling expenses, etc. Because of this benefit people are used to work from home and seems there is a sustainable development of Commerce, Management & also IT sector. It is beneficial from both the point of view – The company as well as the employee. In education field also it is convenient to connect with the students from far away. With the help of Information Technology, Commerce it is very useful to complete the work through online mode and people have also got knowledge to do online work (i.e work from home)

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Introduction:

Work from Home means people have to work from their house,apartment,etc. rather than working from the office.The Work from Home is a basically common thing because of the Disease widely spread across the world i.e CORONA. Because of this pandemic people are habitual and force to work from home.

Objectives:

It is quite common for the people to work from home for their safety.

There are other objectives for work from home- It is a new trend in current scenario.

1. It is help to work more which leads to increased productivity(helpful for employees and employees like)
2. Getting less usage of Electrical power, Vehicle expenses, etc. is saved.
3. Because of this new trend highly motivated to the people of the society and deliver Work from Home agent with outstanding services provided to the customer.
4. It is convenient and comfortable for everyone to work in systematic way.

Content:

Advantages:

1. It is helpful for the people to know the technological work effectively and efficiently also flexible to work
2. Can give more output to the organization as well as give your travelling time to company's growth.
3. In terms of company point of view or employee point of view people are benefitted in monetary terms.
4. Also because of work from home people spend time with their family along with work.
5. Get time for health and happy lifestyle.

Disadvantages:

1. Employees get pressurize by the work as working hours also increased.
2. Co-ordination is increased between the employees during the working hours time.
3. At home people get bored,tired,frustrated,irritated all the time because of work.
4. Unable to learn practical things as all the time working from home.

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Research & Methodology:

As per the review and understanding of the topic it analysed that during the year 2020-21 the crisis acrossed hit the world badly, also it is observed that it is spread widely in the world. There is need to control the disease at the same time take precautionary measures such as wear mask, sanitize self frequently, maintain Six feet distance to others, etc.

Conclusion:

Work from home is a new concept for every citizen at the same time it is get to learn new things, new techniques, and new way to learn new things and at the same time it is growth for the company. The new trend admires people at the same time disappoint the people.

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